

THE MAIN CAUSES OF THYROID PROBLEMS, THEIR SYMPTOMS AND WAYS TO SUPPORT THE ENDOCRINE SYSTEM

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Abstract. *When choosing a topic for the article, I decided to write about one of the most pressing problems of our time - the function of the thyroid gland, the causes of its dysfunction, symptoms of the disease and preventive measures.*

Keywords: *thyroid gland, Hypothyroidism, Hypothyroidism, iodine deficiency in the body - goiter.*

Relevance: One of the main sources that ensure the normal development of the human body is the endocrine system. One of the most common diseases in the endocrine glands is thyroid gland insufficiency.

The function of the thyroid gland is to regulate the following important parameters:

- Body temperature.
- Hunger and appetite.
- Energy storage and consumption.
- Mood.
- Sleep.
- Hormone production.
- Digestion.

Statistics say that today tens of millions of people suffer from various diseases of the thyroid gland.

The most common problem is a decrease in its function – hypotireozis.

Interestingly, in cases of weight gain or rapid fatigue, people do not even entertain the illusion that the cause of this is the thyroid gland and the endocrine system in general.

How do we know if we have a problem with our thyroid gland?

First of all, we try to briefly understand the main mechanisms of the thyroid gland.

The thyroid gland can begin to produce excessive or insufficient amounts of certain hormones for some reason, and in both cases, the thyroid gland can become a serious problem.

The most important thyroid hormones are T3 (triiodothyronine) and T4 (thyroxine).

It is these substances that are needed in the body to convert oxygen and calories into energy, which has an effect on the digestive process and mood.

The most common thyroid problems are:

1. Hypothyroidism - (decreased thyroid gland). Most often, women in the reproductive or middle-aged age (30-50 years) suffer from this disease. With hypotireozis, the body literally slows down. Symptoms include weight gain, brain fog, and lethargy. They occur because the thyroid gland does not produce enough hormones T3 or T4 (or both). This leads to an increase in the level of hormones that stimulate the thyroid gland, in particular - an excess of Thyreotropic hormone.

2. Hyperthyroidism - (overactivity of the thyroid gland). The process is completely contrary to hypothyroidism. Metabolism accelerates to such an extent that tachycardia begins, and weight is gained rapidly.

3. Enlarged thyroid gland – swollen. The main cause of this problem is usually a lack of iodine in the body. Iodine is one of the most important elements for maintaining thyroid gland function.

The most common symptoms of hypothyroidism are:

- Persistent fatigue (often referred to as adrenal fatigue), lethargy, and sometimes depression or low motivation to exercise.

- Bad mood, apathy, drowsiness.

- Dry skin and hair, frost tolerance, toes can even turn purple in some cases.

- Trouble concentrating and forgetfulness.

- An undue increase in body weight.

- Bloating, abdominal discomfort and digestive problems.

- Muscle weakness, sometimes muscle pain.

Symptoms of hyperthyroidism:

- Nervousness

- Insomnia

- Tachycardia.

- Unprovoked weight loss.

- Sweating.

- Muscle weakness.

- Thin, brittle hair.

Signs to look out for before diagnosis:

Dry skin.

Fatigue and lack of concentration.

Cold.

Constipation

Swelling.

Muscle weakness.

Intolerance to exercise.

The main causes of thyroid disorders are:

1. Hashimoto's autoimmune thyroiditis. (AIT) A condition in which the body mistakenly attacks the thyroid gland and destroys its cells, thereby disrupting its structure and functioning. AIT affects women 7-10 times more often than men due to genetic causes. Triggers: Chronic stress, nutritional deficiencies (such as low iodine levels), reduced immunity, and intolerance to certain nutrients.

2. Lack of iodine, selenium, zinc, amino acids, vitamins of group B.

3. Processed products - excessive consumption of sugars and fats.

4. Excessive caffeine or alcohol consumption.

5. Lack of protein and complex carbohydrates.

6. Problems absorbing nutrients from consumed products.

7. Lack of sleep and overtraining.

8. Physical inactivity.

9. Reactions to certain immunosuppressive drugs.

10. Environmental pollution

Solutions:

*Make sure you get enough iodine, selenium, vitamins of group B and zinc. Blood tests will be needed to check for these nutrient levels.

*Substances are contained in the following products:

*Iodine – seafood, algae.

*Selenium - Brazil nuts, spinach, sea fish, lean meat, turkey, beef, liver.

*Zinc - from poultry, beef, eggs, green peas, peas, cocoa, Brussels sprouts, sesame, flax, nuts.

*Manage your emotional reactions to stress and get plenty of rest.

*Limit the irregular intake of medications, the consumption of alcohol and other harmful toxins.

*In hygiene products and cosmetics, use only organic products.

*Pay attention to your daily diet.

*Stop smoking and avoid alcohol.

*Check the environmental cleanliness of the environment.

*Adjust your diet. Get enough protein and complex carbohydrates, omega-3 fatty acids from fish, flax seeds and nuts.

*Try as much as you can, play sports. This eliminates the risk of insulin resistance and allows all the body's energy systems to function without interruptions.

Conclusion

Thus, the activity of the endocrine glands system is considered very relevant and of great importance for the human body. In order to establish public health, it is advisable to intensify preventive work and in-depth study of innovative methods of treatment by health workers in order to eliminate endocrine diseases, especially diseases caused by thyroid disorders, which are most common among the population.

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